

The Direction of Error: Bottom-Up vs. Top-Down Forecast Accuracy Across Independent Atomic Series Under Additive and Averaged Aggregation Regimes

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Targeted Seasonal Forecasts

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Hypothesis

Bottom-Up (atomic) forecasting yields lower aggregate error than Top-Down forecasting, regardless of model type, dataset, or aggregation regime (SUM or AVERAGE).

Datasets

Each dataset contains daily observations with a DATE column and 50 atomic series (one per column after DATE).

- **Flight Delays** — daily counts of departures ≥ 15 minutes late.
- **Air Quality Index (AQI)** — daily AQI values.
- **Temperature** — Daily High Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{F}$).

Datasets are used solely to provide real, independent time-series data for evaluating structural error behavior. No substantive interpretation of the absolute values or units will be made.

Aggregation Structure (Fixed Subsets)

For each dataset, in addition to the 50 atomic series, the study evaluates **fixed subsets** used for both Bottom-Up (BU) and Top-Down (TD) comparisons:

- Five (5) distinct 10-series subsets (“10 \times 5”)
- Two (2) distinct 25-series subsets (“25 \times 2”)
- One (1) 50-series subset (“50 \times 1”)

Subset definitions are created **before** forecasting and remain constant for all months and models.

Each subset is processed **twice**, once per **aggregation regime**:

1. **Additive (SUM)** — each subset’s aggregate = SUM of its atomic series.
2. **Averaged (MEAN)** — each subset’s aggregate = arithmetic MEAN of its atomic series.

Both regimes apply to historical, forecast, and error calculations.

Forecast Cadence & Horizon

- Forecast horizon: 2020-01-01 → 2024-12-31 (inclusive).
 - Cadence: monthly refit, daily predictions.
 - At the start of each month M , models are fit using **all data strictly before the first day of M** .
 - Each monthly refit produces **daily forecasts for every day in M** (one value per date).
 - Process repeats for all 60 months (2020-01 ... 2024-12).
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Forecast Models

1. ARIMA (`auto.arima()`) — automatic ARIMA with seasonal detection.
2. SES (Additive) — Simple Exponential Smoothing, additive errors (zeros allowed).
3. HWES (Additive) — Holt–Winters Exponential Smoothing, additive trend/seasonality (zeros allowed).
4. Mean (Previous-Month) — for month M , every day's forecast equals the **mean of observed values in month $M-1$** (per series).
5. Naïve (Previous-Month) — for month M , every day's forecast equals the **last observed value from the final day of month $M-1$** (per series).

For Mean and Naïve models, training data are limited to the immediately preceding month ($M-1$).

ARIMA, SES, and HWES use all history available up to the start of M .

Paths Compared (per dataset × model × subset × regime)

For each fixed subset (each of the 5×10 , 2×25 , 1×50) and each aggregation regime (SUM, AVERAGE):

1. Bottom-Up (BU)

- Generate daily forecasts for each atomic series in the subset.
- Aggregate (by SUM or MEAN, depending on regime) per day to form the subset's daily BU forecast.

2. Top-Down (TD)

- Create the historical daily aggregate series (SUM or MEAN, matching regime).
- Fit each model to that aggregate series at the start of each month.
- Generate the subset's daily TD forecasts directly at the aggregate level.

Comparison unit: subset-level aggregate (BU vs TD) at daily granularity.

Evaluation Window & Units

- **Training data:** all observations prior to 2020-01-01.
 - **Forecast period:** 2020-01-01 → 2024-12-31 (60 monthly refits; 1,826 forecast days).
 - **Errors computed only at the subset-aggregate level** (never on atomic series).
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Accuracy Metrics (Aggregate Level Only)

For each dataset × model × subset × regime:

- **MAE** — Mean Absolute Error.
- **sMAPE** — Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error.
- **RMSE** — Root Mean Square Error.

Primary effect size: mean difference $\Delta = (\text{TD} - \text{BU})$ for each metric. Positive Δ indicates BU is more accurate (lower error).

Statistical Comparison

For each dataset × model × subset × regime:

1. Compute **daily errors** for TD and BU aggregates.
 2. Summarize: mean MAE, sMAPE, RMSE for TD; same for BU; compute Δ for each.
 3. Compute **win rate** = proportion of forecast days where $|\text{error}|_{\text{BU}} < |\text{error}|_{\text{TD}}$.
 4. Conduct a **paired significance test** (paired t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank) on daily TD vs BU errors.
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Expected Outcome

Across datasets, models, subset sizes, and aggregation regimes, Bottom-Up aggregated forecasts will consistently yield **lower aggregate error** than Top-Down forecasts.

The improvement is expected to increase with subset size (10 → 25 → 50) and to remain directionally consistent under both SUM and AVERAGE aggregation regimes.

Deviations Policy

Any modification to datasets, subset definitions, cadence, aggregation operator definitions, models, or evaluation metrics after registration will be explicitly marked **post-hoc**.

Registration Intent

This preregistration will be publicly posted and timestamped on **Zenodo** or a **public GitHub repository** prior to any forecast generation or accuracy computation.

Post-Hoc Revision – 2025-10-28

Following methodological review, the evaluation framework has been revised to reflect the true atomic structure of accuracy in this study.

Change in unit of analysis

Accuracy is now calculated exclusively at the weekly atomic level. Each forecast month is divided into five fixed weekly buckets (days 1–7, 8–14, 15–21, 22–28, 29–end). Within each bucket, Top-Down (TD) and Bottom-Up (BU) accuracies are computed and compared directly. These weekly values represent the fundamental measurement units for all subsequent analysis.

Aggregation policy

All higher aggregates (monthly, summary) are descriptive only. The monthly tables report the mean of the five weekly percentage differences (TD vs BU) per month. The summary analysis evaluates the series of monthly % differences across the full 60-month horizon to determine directional consistency (e.g., proportion of months $BU < TD$, mean $\Delta\%$).

Retired metrics

No new accuracy metrics are calculated beyond the weekly level. The originally preregistered daily-error statistics (MAE, sMAPE, RMSE) and inferential significance tests (t-tests, p-values, RMSE significance) are retired, as they are no longer applicable to the aggregated framework.

Interpretive scope

Results are now interpreted in descriptive rather than inferential terms—focusing on relative performance patterns (direction, magnitude, and persistence of BU vs TD differences) rather than statistical significance at the daily level.